

1 Source-Resolved Variability of Fine Particulate Matter and 2 Human Exposure in an Urban Area

3
4 Pablo Garcia Rivera¹, Brian T. Dinkelacker¹, Ioannis Kioutsioukis²,
5 Peter J. Adams^{3,4}, and Spyros N. Pandis^{5,6}

6
7 ¹Department of Chemical Engineering, Carnegie Mellon University, Pittsburgh, PA,
8 15213

9 ²Department of Physics, University of Patras, 26500, Patras, Greece

10 ³Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Carnegie Mellon University,
11 Pittsburgh, PA, 15213

12 ⁴Department of Engineering and Public Policy, Carnegie Mellon University, Pittsburgh,
13 PA, 15213

14 ⁵Institute of Chemical Engineering Sciences (FORTH/ICE-HT), 26504, Patras, Greece

15 ⁶Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Patras, 26500, Patras, Greece

16 Corresponding author: Spyros Pandis (spyros@chemeng.upatras.gr)

17 18 **Abstract**

19 Increasing the resolution of chemical transport model (CTM) predictions in urban areas is
20 important to capture sharp spatial gradients in atmospheric pollutant concentrations and
21 better inform air quality and emissions controls policies that protect public health. The
22 chemical transport model PMCAMx was used to assess the impact of increasing model
23 resolution on the ability to predict the source-resolved variability and population exposure
24 to PM_{2.5} at 36 x 36, 12 x 12, 4 x 4, and 1 x 1 km resolutions over the city of Pittsburgh
25 during typical winter and summer periods (February and July 2017). At the coarse
26 resolution, county-level differences can be observed, while increasing the resolution to 12
27 x 12 km resolves the urban-rural gradient. Increasing resolution to 4 x 4 km resolves large
28 stationary sources such as power plants and the 1 x 1 km resolution reveals intra-urban
29 variations and individual roadways within the simulation domain. Regional pollutants that
30 exhibit low spatial variability such as PM_{2.5} nitrate show modest changes when increasing

31 the resolution beyond 12 x 12 km. Predominantly local pollutants such as elemental carbon
32 and primary organic aerosol have gradients that can only be resolved at the 1 x 1 km scale.
33 Contributions from some local sources are enhanced by weighting the average contribution
34 from each source by the population in each grid cell. The average population weighted
35 PM_{2.5} concentration does not change significantly with resolution, suggesting that
36 extremely high resolution PM_{2.5} predictions may not be necessary for effective urban
37 epidemiological analysis.

38

39 **1. Introduction**

40 Particulate matter with aerodynamic diameter less than 2.5 μm (PM_{2.5}) contributes
41 to poor air quality throughout large parts of the United States. These particles directly affect
42 visibility (Seinfeld and Pandis, 2006) and have been associated with long and short-term
43 health effects such as premature death due to cardiovascular disease, increased chance of
44 heart attacks and strokes, and reduced lung development and function in children and
45 people with lung diseases such as asthma (Dockery and Pope, 1994).

46 At high resolutions, emissions from local sources such as commercial cooking, on-
47 road traffic, residential wood combustion, and industrial activities can have sharp gradients
48 that influence the geographical distribution of PM_{2.5} concentrations. High-resolution
49 measurements of PM₁ have found gradients of up to ~2 μg m⁻³ between urban background
50 sites and those with high local emissions (Gu et al., 2018; Robinson et al., 2018).

51 A key limiting factor on the modeling of particulate matter at high resolutions is
52 the geographical distribution of emissions. Previous studies have found that coarse grid
53 emissions interpolated to higher resolutions lead to small to modest improvements in model
54 predictive ability for ozone (Arunachalam et al., 2006; Kumar and Russell, 1996),
55 secondary organic aerosol (Fountoukis et al., 2013; Stroud et al., 2011) and nitrate
56 (Zakoura and Pandis, 2019, 2018). Pan et al., (2017) used the default approach from the
57 U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) National Emissions Inventory (NEI) to
58 allocate county-based emissions to model grid cells at 4 x 4 and 1 x 1 km and found only
59 small changes to model performance for NO_x and O₃, while the 1 x 1 km case showed more
60 detailed features of emissions and concentrations in heavily polluted areas.

61 Improvements in the resolution of emission inventories have been focused on traffic
62 as this source exhibits significant variability at high resolutions. Recent approaches to
63 building high-resolution traffic inventories include origin-destination by vehicle class (Ma
64 et al., 2020), synthetic population mobility (Elessa Etuman and Coll, 2018) and fuel sales
65 combined with traffic counts (McDonald and McBride, 2014). Other sectors such as
66 biomass burning for residential heating and commercial cooking have been identified as
67 very uncertain in current inventories (Day et al., 2019). Recent versions of the NEI have
68 made progress addressing the total emissions and temporal distributions of biomass
69 burning and commercial cooking (Eyth and Vukovich, 2016), but there is still significant
70 uncertainty on their geographical location at a sub-county scale. Robinson et al. (2018)
71 found greatly elevated organic aerosol concentrations (10s of $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) in the vicinity of
72 numerous individual restaurants and commercial districts containing groups of restaurants
73 indicating that commercial cooking is a source of large gradients on the urban scale.

74 Population density and socio-economic indicators of that population, such as
75 income or access to healthcare, show large gradients in the urban scale. It is important to
76 assess the exposure of different sub-populations to air pollutants and the resulting health
77 effects, a concept known as Environmental Justice (Anand, 2002).

78 We use the Particulate Matter Comprehensive Air quality Model with Extensions
79 (PMCAMx) to study the impact of increasing model resolution on the model's ability to
80 predict the variability, sources and population exposure of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentrations on the
81 urban scale in Pittsburgh. We compare predicted variability at 36 x 36, 12 x 12, 4 x 4 and
82 1 x 1 km resolutions over the city of Pittsburgh during one typical summer and one typical
83 winter month of 2017. Additional sensitivity simulations were performed to determine
84 contributions from selected sources to concentrations. The results of the simulations are
85 used to estimate exposure to $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ at all resolutions and from the selected sources. A
86 detailed evaluation of the PMCAMx predictions against measurements will be the topic of
87 a future publication. Overall the model performance was similar to those in previous model
88 applications in the Eastern US (Fountoukis et al., 2013).

89

90 **2. PMCAMx Description**

91 The Particulate Matter Comprehensive Air quality Model with Extensions
92 (PMCAMx) (Karydis et al., 2010; Murphy and Pandis, 2009; Tsimpidi et al., 2010), uses
93 the framework of the CAMx model (Environ, 2006) to describe horizontal and vertical
94 advection and diffusion, emissions, wet and dry deposition, gas, aqueous and aerosol-phase
95 chemistry. A 10-size section aerosol sectional approach is used to dynamically track the
96 evolution of the aerosol mass distribution. The aerosol species modeled include sulfate,
97 nitrate, ammonium, sodium, chloride, elemental carbon, water, primary and secondary
98 organics, and other non-volatile aerosol components. The SAPRC (Statewide Air Pollution
99 Research Center) photochemical mechanism (Carter, 1999) is used for the simulation of
100 gas-phase chemistry. The version of SAPRC used here includes 237 reactions and 91
101 individual and surrogate species. For inorganic growth, a bulk equilibrium approach was
102 used, assuming equilibrium between the bulk inorganic aerosol and gas phases (Pandis et
103 al., 1993). Aqueous-phase chemistry is simulated using the Variable Size Resolution
104 Model (VSRM) (Fahey and Pandis, 2001). The partitioning of the various semivolatile
105 inorganic aerosol components and aerosol water is determined using the ISORROPIA-I
106 aerosol thermodynamics model (Nenes et al., 1998). The primary and secondary organic
107 aerosol components are described using the volatility basis set approach (Donahue et al.,
108 2006). For primary organic aerosol (POA) ten volatility bins, with effective saturation
109 concentrations ranging from 10^{-3} to $10^6 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 298 K are used. The volatility distribution
110 for POA from Tsimpidi et al. (2010) was used for all sources, while size distributions are
111 specific to each emission sector. Anthropogenic (aSOA) and biogenic (bSOA) are modeled
112 with 4 volatility bins (1, 10, 10^2 , $10^3 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) (Murphy and Pandis, 2009) using NO_x
113 dependent yields (Lane et al., 2008). Both fine and coarse PM are simulated by PMCAMx,
114 although the following analysis in this work is focused on fine PM. More detailed
115 descriptions of PMCAMx can be found in Fountoukis et al. (2011) and Zakoura and Pandis
116 (2018).

117

118 **3. Model Application**

119 PMCAMx was used to simulate air quality over the metropolitan area of Pittsburgh
120 during February and July 2017. For the base-case simulation we used a one-way nested

121 structure with a 36 x 36 km master grid covering the continental United States, with nested
122 grids of 12 x 12 km, 4 x 4 km in South Western Pennsylvania and a 1 x 1 km grid covering
123 the city of Pittsburgh, most of Allegheny County and the upper Ohio River valley (Figure
124 1a). The 1 x 1 km grid covers a 72 x 72 km area (Figure 1b). Two days in each simulation
125 were used for model spin-up and discarded for all analyses. Simulations required
126 approximately 6 CPU days, 5 CPU hours, 10 CPU hours, and 12 CPU days to complete in
127 a single Intel Xeon CPU E5-4640 at 2.4 GHz for the 36 km, 12 km, 4 km, and 1 km
128 domains, respectively.

129 The surface concentrations at the boundaries of the 36 x 36 km grid are shown in
130 Table S1 in the Supplementary Information. These values were applied to all upper air
131 layers assuming a constant mixing ratio. Results from lower resolution simulations were
132 used as boundary conditions for the corresponding next higher resolution simulation.
133 Horizontal wind components, vertical diffusivity, temperature, pressure, water vapor,
134 clouds, and rainfall were generated using the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF
135 v3.6.1) model over the whole modeling domain with horizontal resolution of 12 km. The
136 data was interpolated to higher resolutions when needed. The interpolation of
137 meteorological fields from 12 x 12 km to higher resolutions is a potential limitation of this
138 work and will be the focus of future improvements to the modeling methods. Initial and
139 boundary meteorological conditions for the WRF simulations were generated from the
140 ERA-Interim global climate re-analysis database, together with the terrestrial data sets for
141 terrain height, land-use, soil categories, etc. from the United States Geological Survey
142 (USGS) database. The WRF modeling system was prepared and configured in a similar
143 way as described by Gilliam and Pleim (2010). This configuration is recommended for air
144 quality simulations (Hogrefe et al., 2015; Rogers et al., 2013). 28 vertical layers were used
145 in the WRF simulations to produce 14 layers of meteorological input for the PMCAMx
146 simulations. Each of the 14 PMCAMx layers corresponds to a WRF layer.

147 Emissions were calculated using the EPA's Emission Modeling Platform (v6.3) for
148 the National Emissions Inventory for 2011 (NEI11) (Eyth and Vukovich, 2016) using the
149 default 2017 projected values. Base emissions were calculated first at a 12 km resolution
150 for the full modeling domain using the Sparse Matrix Operator Kernel Emissions
151 (SMOKE) model and our WRF meteorological data. The data sources used to produce 12

152 km resolution surrogates with Platform v6.3 were used to develop surrogates at 4 x 4 km
153 and 1 x 1 km resolution for all sectors except commercial cooking and on-road traffic for
154 which custom surrogates were developed. These custom surrogates also use projected
155 values for 2017. Bicubic interpolation was used to produce biogenic emissions at 4 x 4 km
156 and 1 x 1 km resolution, in areas in which sufficient data was unavailable. The emissions
157 by all sources together with the chemical composition are summarized in Tables 1 (for the
158 winter period) and 2 (for the summer period)..

159 In this work, we used normalized restaurant count to distribute the commercial
160 cooking emissions in space in the 1x1 km and 4x4 km resolution domains. Geographical
161 information was collected for all locations labeled as “restaurant” from the freely
162 accessible Google Places Application Programming Interface (API) for the western
163 Pennsylvania area, eastern Ohio and northern West Virginia. Using this new spatial
164 surrogate, PM_{2.5} emissions from commercial cooking are enhanced primarily in the
165 Pittsburgh urban core with a maximum increase of 1200 kg d⁻¹ km⁻² (Figure 2a).

166 To accurately capture spatial patterns of on-road traffic, we use the output of a link-
167 level, origin-destination by vehicle class traffic model of Pittsburgh (Ma et al., 2020). This
168 traffic model simulates traffic counts and speed by hour-of-day using observations from
169 Pennsylvania Department of Transportation sites throughout Pittsburgh. As expected,
170 emissions in areas with major highways are high (Figure 2b).

171 The novel surrogates used for onroad traffic and cooking result in increases in
172 emissions in some areas and particularly in downtown Pittsburgh and decreases in others.
173 Total emissions inside the inner 1 x 1 km domain are the same using both the new and old
174 surrogates. For commercial cooking, emissions calculated using the new surrogates are
175 more concentrated in areas with high restaurant densities such as downtown Pittsburgh and
176 the Oakland neighborhood (Figures S1 and S2). For onroad traffic, the emissions become
177 higher at the locations of major highways and in the urban area of Pittsburgh when using
178 the new surrogates (Figures S3 and S4). Using the new spatial distribution of emissions
179 predicted average PM_{2.5} increase by 1-2 µg m⁻³ at certain areas. A detailed evaluation of
180 these predictions will be the topic of another publication.

181

182 **4. PM_{2.5} concentrations and sources during winter**

183 **4.1 Effect of grid resolution**

184 The results of the simulations with the four resolutions for the winter period are
185 shown in Figures 3 and 4. For the area of interest, the simulations at 36 x 36 km resolves
186 concentration fields at the county scale. The urban-rural gradient is resolved in the 12 x 12
187 km simulations. Increasing the resolution to 4 x 4 km, large stationary sources such as
188 power plants and large industrial installations are resolved. Finally, the resolution increase
189 to 1 x 1 km resolves the intra-urban variations in Pittsburgh and medium-sized industrial
190 installations. Variable concentration limits are used in the species maps to remove
191 background and highlight the effects of local sources (Figures 3 and 4).

192 In the winter period, the predicted maximum PM_{2.5} concentration in the inner
193 domain increases from 10.4 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 36x36 km, to 11.8 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 12x12, to 12.9 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at
194 4x4, and finally to 16.4 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 1x1 km (Figure 3), a 58% increase. On the other end, the
195 predicted minimum PM_{2.5} concentration changes from 8.2 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 36 x 36 km to 7 μg
196 m^{-3} at 12 x 12 and remains practically the same at even higher resolutions. This corresponds
197 to the “background” concentration level for the area during the simulation period, so further
198 resolution enhancements do not change this value. The standard deviation of the predicted
199 concentration can be used as a measure of the concentration variability in the area. This
200 standard deviation changes from 0.9 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 36x36, to 1.24 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 12x12, to 1.45 μg
201 m^{-3} at 4x4 and to 1.35 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 1x1 km. These results indicate an increase of the PM_{2.5}
202 variability by 50% when one moves from the coarse to the finest resolution. However, most
203 of this change in variability (38% out of the 50%) appears when one moves from 36x36 to
204 12x12 km.

205 Elemental carbon is a primary aerosol component with sources that are quite
206 variable in space. In winter, the predicted maximum PM_{2.5} EC increased by a factor of 2.9,
207 from 0.6 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at the 36 x 36 km resolution to 1.6 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 1 x 1 km (Figure 3). The
208 predicted maximum EC is, as expected in the Pittsburgh downtown area. On the other hand,
209 the predicted minimum of EC is reduced by only 0.1 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, from 0.34 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 36x36
210 km to 0.24 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at resolutions lower or equal than 4x4 km. The standard deviation of the
211 predicted EC almost doubles from 0.1 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 36 x 36 km to 0.18 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 1 x 1 km.
212 Approximately 50% of this increase in variability appears in the transition from the coarse

213 to the intermediate resolution of 12 x 12 km. The fine and the finest resolutions are needed
214 to resolve the other half of the predicted variability.

215 During this winter period a significant fraction (79%) of the OA in the Pittsburgh
216 area is primary and therefore the higher resolution results in increases of the predicted
217 maximum concentrations in space from 2.8 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at the coarse resolution to 3.7 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at
218 the intermediate to 4.8 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at the finest resolution (Figure 3). This corresponds to an
219 increase by a factor of 1.7, more than the change for total $\text{PM}_{2.5}$, but much less than that
220 for EC. The predicted maximum is located in downtown Pittsburgh, with additional
221 hotspots in neighboring counties that are resolved at the fine and finest resolution. The
222 predicted minimum changes from 2.1 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 36x36 to 1.7 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 12x12 with small
223 reductions at higher resolutions. The variability (standard deviation) of the OA
224 concentration field of the predicted concentration increases by a factor of approximately
225 1.6 from 0.35 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 36 x 36, to 0.51 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 12 x 12 km. The increase is small at even
226 higher resolutions with the standard deviation of OA reaching 0.53 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 1 x 1 km (an
227 increase by a factor of 1.7).

228 Average predicted $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ sulfate in the inner domain changes little between the
229 coarsest resolution (average level 1.37 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) and finest resolution (1.29 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$). The
230 minimum concentration decreased slightly with resolution from 1.33 to 1.2 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, with
231 much of the decrease captured by increasing the resolution to 12 x 12 km. The maximum
232 sulfate concentration increased by a larger value but this change was not observed until
233 moving to the highest resolution where the maximum was 2.08 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, compared to 1.4
234 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 36 x 36 km resolution. The standard deviation increased only marginally from
235 0.03 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 36 x 36 km to 0.06 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 1 x 1 km. The low variability in the predicted
236 ground sulfate levels during the winter is partially due to the low mixing heights during
237 this cold period with the emissions from the tall stacks of local power generation sources
238 often introduced above the boundary layer.

239 The predicted fine nitrate levels are relatively high ranging from 1.78 to 2.24 μg
240 m^{-3} in the coarse-resolution simulation. This is expected in this wintertime period due to
241 the partitioning of nitric acid and ammonium in the particulate phase. This predicted
242 concentration range increases to 1.5-2.24 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in the finest scale simulation with higher
243 levels in the northeast of the domain. The standard deviation of the predicted concentration

244 does not show any significant trend changing from $0.19 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 36×36 to $0.15 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$
245 at 1×1 km.

246 For $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ ammonium, changes with increasing resolution are modest with the
247 predicted minimum being reduced from $1.07 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 36×36 to approximately $0.95 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$
248 m^{-3} at all other higher resolutions. The predicted maximum stays relatively constant
249 between $1.25 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and $1.27 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at all resolutions. As with nitrate, the standard
250 deviation does not show any significant trend changing from $0.08 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 36×36 , to 0.09
251 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 12×12 , to $0.07 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 4×4 and 1×1 km resolutions.

252

253 **4.2 Source Apportionment**

254 We performed zero-out simulations in the 1×1 km Pittsburgh grid to determine the
255 local contributions of eight source categories to the total $\text{PM}_{2.5}$. The local sources
256 quantified included: commercial cooking, industrial, biomass burning, on-road traffic,
257 power generation, and miscellaneous area sources. A summary of total local (within the
258 inner 1×1 km resolution domain) dry $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ emissions from each source category during
259 February 2017 is shown in Table 1. The species category labeled “other” for the power
260 generation sector is predominately composed of ash (including metals emitted from power
261 generation) and is simulated in PMCAMx as inert particle mass. Biomass burning
262 emissions here correspond only to residential wood combustion, as there were no
263 significant wildfires in the 1×1 km resolution domain during the simulation periods. The
264 $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ emissions used in this study contain both the condensable and filterable fractions of
265 $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ (U.S. EPA, 2015). The miscellaneous area sources sector includes a large variety of
266 emission sources that are not classified in any of the sources in Table 1. These include
267 chemical manufacturing, solvent utilization for surface coatings, degreasing and dry
268 cleaning, storage and transport of petroleum products, waste disposal and incineration, and
269 cremation. The emissions from agricultural dust, river barges, off-road equipment, oil-gas
270 activities, and rail were grouped on the “others” source. All emissions (particulate and gas-
271 phase) from each source were set to zero, and the results of the zero-out simulation were
272 subtracted from those of the baseline simulation to estimate the corresponding source
273 contribution. The contribution of long-range transport from outside the inner domain was
274 also estimated by setting all local sources to zero.

275 Biomass burning is used during the winter for residential heating and recreation.
276 This source contributes a maximum of $3.31 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in Cranberry, a northern suburb of
277 Pittsburgh located in the neighboring Butler county. In the downtown Pittsburgh area, the
278 contribution from biomass burning accounts for 7% of the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$. This source shows the
279 highest variability with a standard deviation of $0.5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$.

280 The maximum contribution of $8.05 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ from industry is predicted near a cluster
281 of industrial facilities in the town of Beaver, 37 km northwest of Pittsburgh. The maximum
282 $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration of the modeling domain is located here. In this location long-range
283 transport contributes 37% of the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ followed by industrial sources with 49% and
284 biomass burning with 7%. On average, the contribution from industrial sources is low with
285 3.7%. In downtown Pittsburgh, the contribution is lower still with 2%.

286 On-road traffic emissions are most important in major highway intersections and
287 river crossings surrounding downtown Pittsburgh with a maximum contribution of $3.9 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$
288 accounting for 24% of the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ in this area. On average, on-road traffic contributes
289 2.5% of the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ mass. The contribution from on-road traffic shows higher variability
290 (standard deviation: $0.36 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) since this sector contributes significantly to areas adjacent
291 to the network of highways that radiates from the Pittsburgh downtown.

292 On average, commercial cooking emissions contribute 0.7% of the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ in the
293 modeling domain with a maximum contribution of $2.44 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in downtown Pittsburgh,
294 with smaller contributions in the surrounding urban area. Cooking is predicted to account
295 for 16% of the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ mass in downtown Pittsburgh. The contribution from commercial
296 cooking is localized around downtown Pittsburgh and therefore shows little variability
297 throughout the domain with a standard deviation of $0.1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$.

298 The miscellaneous area source sector contributes 6% of the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ on average. Since
299 this sector encompasses a variety of sources and activities, its contribution shows
300 significant variability with a standard deviation of $0.34 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. The maximum contribution
301 is located in the Pittsburgh urban core with $1.64 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, accounting for 11% of the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$.

302 The power generation sector contributes a maximum of $0.63 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in the plume
303 of the Bruce Mansfield power plant northwest of Pittsburgh (this plant is no longer
304 operating as of 2019). The contribution of this sector shows the smallest variability at 0.09
305 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. The contribution to ground $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ from power generation in the winter is relatively

306 low. This is largely due to the height of the emissions stacks associated with this sector. A
307 significant fraction of the emissions from power generation is trapped above the shallow
308 mixing height in the winter and much of the PM_{2.5} mass is predicted to remain in the upper
309 air layers. The predicted relative high upper air PM_{2.5} concentration from power generation
310 are shown in Figure S5.

311 Long-range transport from outside the inner modeling domain is the major source
312 of PM_{2.5} during this period contributing an average of 74%. This contribution varies from
313 7.1 μg m⁻³ in the southeast corner of the domain decreasing in the direction of the Pittsburgh
314 urban core where the contribution is reduced to 5.9 μg m⁻³. In areas where there are
315 significant local emissions such as the Pittsburgh downtown, the contribution from long-
316 range transport decreases to 38%.

317 Contributions for all remaining sources are largest in the Pittsburgh downtown with
318 0.74 μg m⁻³, accounting for 5% of the PM_{2.5}. This sector also significantly contributes on
319 the Ohio and Monongahela river valleys, where there is important rail and river traffic. On
320 average, these sources contribute 3% of the PM_{2.5} and show a moderate variability with a
321 standard deviation of 0.1 μg m⁻³.

322 For all local sources, the minimum contribution is close to zero (less than 0.1 μg
323 m⁻³) and is located at the southwestern corner of the domain, near the Ohio – West Virginia
324 border.

325

326 **5. PM_{2.5} concentrations and sources during summer**

327 **5.1 Effect of grid resolution**

328 The predicted PM_{2.5} concentrations in the simulated summer period are lower than
329 during the winter period and more uniform, however, the qualitative behavior of the model
330 at the different scales remains the same (Figure 6). Variable concentration limits are again
331 used in these maps to remove background and highlight the effects of local sources. The
332 standard deviation of the PM_{2.5} increases from 0.28 μg m⁻³ at 36 x 36, to 0.57 μg m⁻³ at 12
333 x 12, to 0.72 μg m⁻³ at 4 x 4 and to 0.82 μg m⁻³ at 1 x 1 km. At the finest scale, the predicted
334 variability in the summer is 61% of that in the winter. Similar to the winter period, the
335 predicted maximum PM_{2.5} concentration changes significantly with increasing resolution.
336 The predicted maximum PM_{2.5} increases from 6.4 μg m⁻³ at the coarse to 15.3 μg m⁻³ at the

337 fine resolution. The finest scale better resolves the concentration field in the cluster of
338 industrial installations 37 km northwest of Pittsburgh. The minimum $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ drops from 6.5
339 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 36×36 to $5.3 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 12×12 , and then to $4.7 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 1×1 km. As in the
340 winter period, the moderate resolution appears to capture the majority of the concentration
341 change from increasing resolution (67%).

342 The average EC is lower during the summer with $0.28 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ versus $0.43 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$
343 in the winter. The standard deviation of the predicted average EC increases from $0.06 \mu\text{g}$
344 m^{-3} at 36×36 , to $0.09 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 12×12 , to $0.11 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 4×4 km, and to $0.13 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at
345 1×1 km. The peak average EC is located in downtown Pittsburgh and increases by a factor
346 of 3.6 (from 0.35 to $1.27 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) moving from the coarse to the finest resolution. It is
347 noteworthy that the peak is 38% less than that of the winter when the coarse resolution is
348 used, but only 21% when the finest resolution is used. The concentration range (difference
349 between the maximum and the minimum) increases from $0.13 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ to $1.12 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$
350 moving from the coarse to the finest resolution. This increase by a factor of 8.6 shows the
351 importance of the local variations of a primary species like EC in an urban area in both
352 summer and winter.

353 The OA concentration field is quite uniform at the coarse-scale varying by only
354 $0.17 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ (from 1.72 to $1.89 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) with a standard deviation of $0.07 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ (Figure 6).
355 Variability increases significantly when one moves to the finest scale, with the range
356 increasing to $2.24 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ (from 1.55 to $3.79 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) and the standard deviation of the OA
357 field increases to $0.2 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. The use of the finest scale appears to be needed for the
358 resolution of the OA high concentration areas in the summer more than in the winter.

359 The $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ sulfate levels during the summer period are on average 12% higher
360 during the summertime period. At the coarse and intermediate scales, the predicted average
361 concentration fields have relatively little structure (Figure 7). The corresponding
362 concentration ranges are relatively narrow ($0.05 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 36×36 km and $0.42 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at
363 12×12 km). However, a different picture emerges at the fine and especially the finest scales.
364 The plumes from the major power plants can be clearly seen at these higher resolutions.
365 The maximum increased by $0.5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ from the coarse scale to the finest scale while the
366 minimum is reduced from $1.78 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 36×36 to $1.05 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 12×12 , to $0.95 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$
367 at 4×4 and 1×1 km. The standard deviation of the predicted sulfate concentration field

368 at the coarse resolution is low and similar to that in winter, $0.02 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. However, the
369 variability at the finest scale in the summer ($0.13 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at $1 \times 1 \text{ km}$) is twice the predicted
370 variability in the winter.

371 The predicted summertime nitrate concentrations are quite low in the area (average
372 $0.5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in the coarse and $0.46 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in the finest resolution). The predicted minimum
373 decreases from $0.42 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 36×36 to $0.39 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 12×12 , to $0.34 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 4×4 , and
374 to $0.3 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at $1 \times 1 \text{ km}$. The predicted maximum concentration increases from $0.56 \mu\text{g}$
375 m^{-3} at the coarse scale to $0.71 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at the intermediate scale and stays relatively constant
376 at higher resolutions. The concentration field is quite uniform with a standard deviation
377 ranging from 0.06 to $0.09 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ for all scales. However, due to the reduction in the
378 predicted minimum the concentration range increases from $0.14 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at the coarse
379 resolution to $0.37 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at the finest resolution.

380 The $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ ammonium concentration field is quite uniform at all resolutions (Figure
381 7). The concentration range increases from 0.04 to $0.22 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ moving from the coarse to
382 the finest resolution and the standard deviation increases from 0.02 to $0.04 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$.

383

384 **5.2 Source Apportionment**

385 The local emissions for each source category during July 2017 are shown in Table
386 2. During summer, residential biomass burning is minimal. This source contributes a
387 maximum of $0.04 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and an average of $0.007 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, accounting for 0.6% of the
388 average total $\text{PM}_{2.5}$.

389 Power generation sources have the highest average contribution to total $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ of
390 all the local sources of 10%. Industrial sources account for 6% of the average $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ but are
391 the most important contributor in the point of the modeling domain with the maximum
392 predicted $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration. At this location in Beaver County, industrial sources account
393 for 58% of total $\text{PM}_{2.5}$.

394 As in the winter period, on-road traffic emissions have the largest contribution to
395 the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ in the downtown Pittsburgh area where four large highways intersect. In this
396 location on-road traffic contributes 26% of the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$. On average, local on-road traffic
397 contributes around 3% of the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ mass. During the summer period, the variability of the

398 on-road traffic contribution is slightly lower with $0.33 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ compared with $0.36 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$
399 during winter.

400 Commercial cooking emissions contribute a maximum of $2.08 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ to the
401 average total $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ in downtown Pittsburgh. This source accounts for 17% of the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ in
402 the city but only 1% for the entire modeling domain. The large predicted contribution from
403 cooking $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ is consistent with the mobile AMS measurements performed by Ye et al.
404 (2018), that indicated that cooking organic aerosol contributes up to 60% of the non-
405 refractory PM_1 mass. Mobile AMS results from Gu et al. (2018) showed that cooking OA
406 contributes 5-20% of PM_1 mass over multiple areas in the city of Pittsburgh. Other
407 measurements in Pittsburgh also showed that cooking OA concentrations were clearly
408 elevated in the vicinity of restaurants when compared with residential areas (Robinson et
409 al., 2018). Though the cooking $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ mass predictions of our study cannot be directly
410 compared to these measurements, they all highlight the local importance of cooking as a
411 fine PM pollution source.

412 On average, the miscellaneous area sources sector contributes $0.26 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$
413 accounting for 4.3% of the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$. In downtown Pittsburgh, where the contribution is
414 highest, this source contributes 7% of the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$.

415 Unlike in the winter period, the plumes from major powerplants in the Ohio river
416 valley are clearly resolved in the summer. The power generation sector contributes a
417 maximum of $2.4 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in the plume of the Bruce Mansfield power plant northwest of
418 Pittsburgh. On average, the 9.4% contribution from this sector to the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ is much larger
419 than in the winter where it only contributed 2.3%. The plume from the Mitchell power
420 plant in the southwest corner of the modeling domain is clearly resolved and reaches all
421 the way to the city. This increases the contribution from power generation to the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ in
422 the downtown core from $0.22 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in the winter to $0.61 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in the summer. The
423 maximum contribution of $8.98 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ from industrial sources is a cluster of industrial
424 facilities in the town of Beaver, northwest of Pittsburgh.

425 Long-range transport from sources outside the region contributes a maximum of
426 $5.2 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in the southeast corner of the domain decreasing in the direction of the Pittsburgh
427 northern suburbs where the contribution is minimal with $4.1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. On average, long-
428 range transport accounts for 72% of the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ mass. In downtown Pittsburgh, long-range

429 transport contributes $4.24 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ accounting for 35% of the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$. The high-concentration
430 area visible on the western edge of the domain is due to a cluster of power generation and
431 industrial sources located in the Ohio River valley just outside of the inner modeling
432 domain.

433 On average, the contribution from all remaining sources is 3.6% and shows a
434 moderate variability of $0.1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. The contribution from these sources is maximal in
435 downtown Pittsburgh with $0.78 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ accounting for 6% of the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$.

436 For all local sources, the minimum contribution is close to zero (less than $0.1 \mu\text{g}$
437 m^{-3}) and is located at the northwestern corner of the domain, near the Ohio – Pennsylvania
438 border.

439 Relative contributions of all local sources to domain average predicted total $\text{PM}_{2.5}$
440 (including long-range transport $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ mass) are shown in Figure 9. The largest differences
441 between February and July are the contributions from biomass burning and power
442 generation. In the winter, biomass burning is the most important local source of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$,
443 contributing over 8%. In the summer, this source contributes much less than 1% to total
444 $\text{PM}_{2.5}$. This discrepancy can easily be explained by the lack of residential wood combustion
445 in the warmer months of the year. Power generation is a significantly more important
446 source in July than in February. This is likely a result of a lower mixing height in the winter
447 combined with emissions plumes from power plants in the Ohio river vally originating
448 from very tall stacks.

449 The relative contributions of local sources to average predicted total $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ in the
450 maximum concentration cell in Beaver County and in downtown Pittsburgh are shown in
451 Figures 10 and 11, respectively. The dominant local source in the Beaver County location
452 is industrial emissions, due to the proximity of various industrial installations in this area.
453 Industrial sources here account for around 49% of total $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ in February and 58% of total
454 $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ in July. A lot of the difference in industrial $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ at the Beaver County location
455 between months is made up by biomass burning in February, which accounts for 7% more
456 of the total compared to July. In the downtown area of Pittsburgh, the majority of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$
457 from local sources can be attributed to either traffic (22-27% of total $\text{PM}_{2.5}$) or cooking
458 (16-18% of total $\text{PM}_{2.5}$) in both simulation periods (Figure 11).

459

460 **6. Exposure to PM_{2.5}**

461 The population data in the inner domain from the 2010 U.S. census was used to
462 estimate the exposure of the population in the Pittsburgh area to model predictions of PM_{2.5}
463 during winter of 2017 at the different grid resolutions. We ranked the average PM_{2.5}
464 concentrations from all the cells in the modeling domain and created bins of 0.2 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. A
465 sum of the population from all the grid cells that fall within each concentration bin was
466 calculated and divided by the total population of the inner grid to construct population
467 exposure histograms. The population data used here is resolved at the census group level,
468 which is much smaller than the simulation grid cell size of 1 x 1 km.

469

470 **6.1 Winter PM_{2.5} Exposure**

471 Figure 12 shows the population exposure histograms for the Pittsburgh area (inner
472 domain) for each model resolution. At the coarse resolution, there are only four PM_{2.5}
473 values and 46% of the population is exposed to a concentration of 10.4 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ with
474 decreasing exposure with PM_{2.5} concentration. At a 12 km resolution, the low
475 concentration side of the distribution is better resolved but gaps can still be observed at
476 higher levels. At this intermediate resolution, the largest fraction of the population (15%)
477 is exposed to PM_{2.5} concentrations of 11.8 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$.

478 When the resolution is increased to 4 km the biggest improvements on the model
479 ability to resolve the exposure distribution happen at concentrations higher than 9.4 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$
480 m^{-3} . At the fine resolution, no gaps appear in the distribution. A maximum of 12% of the
481 population is exposed to PM_{2.5} concentrations of 12 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ while at the highest
482 concentration of 12.8 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ 3% are exposed. At the 1 km resolution, the distribution is
483 much smoother due to the ability of this finest grid to capture local gradients. The largest
484 fraction of the population (6%) is exposed to PM_{2.5} concentrations of 9.2 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. At the
485 highest concentration of 14.4 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ the exposed population is less than 0.1% as this
486 maximum point is located near industrial installations 37 km northwest of Pittsburgh where
487 the population density is very low.

488 The differences between the predicted exposure distributions at 4 km and 1 km
489 resolutions highlight the need for high resolution modeling studies in order to identify key
490 areas from the environmental justice perspective. The upper tail of the exposure

491 distribution ($13\text{--}14\ \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) is only detectable at the 1 km resolution. These higher
492 exposures could be addressed by appropriate targeted regulations, because they are the
493 direct result of proximity to either major industrial and electrical generation sources or
494 dense traffic and cooking emissions.

495 At resolutions of 36 km, 12 km, 4 km, and 1 km the predicted average population
496 weighted total $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration during February 2017 is $9.74\ \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, $9.77\ \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, 10.28
497 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, and $10.00\ \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, respectively. This represents an increase of only 2.6% when
498 moving from lowest to highest resolution. Relative contributions of local sources to
499 average population weighted $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration is shown in Figure 14. Compared to the
500 domain average $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentrations (Figure 9), many local source contributions are
501 enhanced in terms of average population exposure. In February, weighting $\text{PM}_{2.5}$
502 concentrations by population increases the contribution from biomass burning from 8.3%
503 to 11.7%. Other notable increases include onroad traffic (2.5% to 6.5%), and miscellaneous
504 area sources (5.9% to 9.2%). Other local source contributions to population weighted $\text{PM}_{2.5}$
505 were similar to the corresponding non-weighted concentrations.

506 The source-resolved population exposure distributions during this winter period are
507 shown in Figures S6 and S7.

508

509 **6.2 Summer $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ Exposure**

510 Figure 13 shows the population exposure for each simulation grid during the
511 summer period. At the coarse resolution, 88% of the population is exposed to a
512 concentration of 7 to $7.2\ \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. At 12×12 km resolution, the exposure distribution is
513 better resolved but a gap is still present at $7.2\ \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and exposure to $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentrations
514 above $7.6\ \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ is not resolved at all. At this intermediate resolution, the largest fraction
515 of the population (19%) is exposed to $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentrations of $7.4\ \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. Increasing the
516 resolution to 4×4 km both shifts the distribution to slightly lower concentrations and
517 resolves exposure to higher $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentrations than with the 12×12 km grid. At this
518 resolution, 14% of the population is exposed to $6.4\ \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and smaller portions of the
519 population are exposed to concentrations higher than $8.0\ \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. Moving to the highest
520 resolution grid further resolves the exposure distribution. Most notably, 1×1 km resolution
521 reveals a bimodal distribution of population exposure, with one peak centered around 6.0

522 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and another centered around $7.4 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. This likely corresponds to one subset of
523 the population in the urban areas of Pittsburgh who are exposed to higher $\text{PM}_{2.5}$
524 concentrations and another subset representing the surrounding suburban areas.

525 In the summer period, an even larger range of high-concentration exposure is
526 revealed moving from 4 km to 1 km resolution. At this high resolution, the population
527 exposure to concentrations ranging from $8.5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ to $12 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ becomes clear. Most people
528 exposed to these higher fine PM levels according to PMCAMx live in the vicinity of the
529 industrial complexes and power stations around the city of Beaver. The higher
530 concentration range of the upper tail of the exposure during July compared to February is
531 due to a large extent to the effective mixing of the emissions from the tall stacks down to
532 the ground level.

533 At resolutions of 36 km, 12 km, 4 km, and 1 km the predicted average population
534 weighted total $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration during February 2017 is $7.06 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, $6.78 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, 7.0
535 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, and $6.99 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, respectively. This represents just a 1% decrease between the
536 lowest and highest resolutions. Similar to the effect seen in February, weighting $\text{PM}_{2.5}$
537 concentrations by population increases the contribution from onroad traffic from 3.3% to
538 8.9% in July. Contributions from miscellaneous area sources also increased (4.3% to 7.1%)
539 when weighting by population. The population weighted contribution from power
540 generation sources in July decreased from the non-weighted value from 9.4% to 8.3%. All
541 other local source contributions to population weighted $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ in July were similar to the
542 non-weighted values.

543 The source-resolved population exposure distributions during this summer period are
544 shown in Figures S8 and S9.

545

546 **7. Conclusions**

547 We applied the PMCAMx chemical transport model over the city of Pittsburgh for
548 the simulation periods of February and July 2017 using a series of telescoping grids at 36
549 x 36 km, 12 x 12 km, 4 x 4 km and 1 x 1 km. Emissions were calculated using 2017
550 projections from the 2011 NEI. Emissions were distributed geographically using the spatial
551 surrogates provided with the NEI11 for all grids. For commercial cooking, a new 1 x 1 km
552 spatial surrogate was developed using restaurant count data from the Google Places API.

553 Traffic model data was used to develop a 1 x 1 km spatial surrogate for on-road traffic
554 emissions.

555 At the coarse resolution, county-level differences can be observed. Increasing the
556 resolution to 12 x 12 km resolves the urban-rural gradient and further increasing to 4 x 4
557 resolves large stationary sources such as power plants. Only at the finest resolution intra-
558 urban variations and individual roadways are resolved. Low variability, regional pollutants
559 such as nitrate show limited improvement after increasing the resolution to 12 x 12 km
560 while predominantly local pollutants such as elemental carbon and winter organic aerosol
561 have gradients that can only be resolved at the finest resolution.

562 Biomass burning shows the largest variability during the winter period with many
563 local maxima and significant emissions within the city and in the suburbs. During the
564 summer contributions from this source are negligible. In contrast with the winter period,
565 during the summer the plumes from large power plants in the Ohio river valley can be
566 resolved. These plumes are rich in sulfates and start being resolved at 4 x 4 km with
567 significant detail added at 1 x 1 km. During both periods the largest contributing source to
568 the average PM_{2.5} is particles from outside the modeling domain.

569 The ability of the model to resolve the exposure distribution increases at different
570 rates according to the concentration. A significant improvement in resolving exposure to
571 concentrations below 9.4 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in the winter and below 7.0 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in the summer is
572 achieved by increasing the resolution to 12 x 12 km. Only at the finest resolution is the
573 exposure to concentrations above 9.6 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in the winter and above 8.6 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in the
574 summer fully resolved as well as the impact of high concentration spots.

575 The average exposure in terms of average contribution to population weighted
576 PM_{2.5} concentrations of some local sources is enhanced compared to the non-weighted
577 average PM_{2.5} concentrations. In February, weighting by population enhanced the
578 contributions from biomass burning, onroad traffic, and miscellaneous area sources by 3-
579 4%. In July, the contributions from onroad traffic and miscellaneous area sources also
580 increased by 3-5% from this procedure.

581 It was determined that increasing simulation grid resolution from 36 x 36 km to 1
582 x 1 km had minimal effect on the predicted domain average population weighted PM_{2.5}
583 concentration. Moving from the lowest to highest grid resolution increased the predicted

584 average population weighted $PM_{2.5}$ by less than 3%. In July, the average decreased by 1%.
585 This negligible change in the predicted average exposure to $PM_{2.5}$ suggests that extremely
586 high resolution predictions of urban $PM_{2.5}$ pollution may not be necessary for accurate
587 epidemiological analysis in the absence of high-resolution health data. However it is also
588 clear that the average population-weighted concentration approach misses the potentially
589 important impacts of large sources on small communities. The increased neighborhood
590 scale resolution is vital for identifying communities that are disproportionately exposed to
591 large sources of $PM_{2.5}$ pollution, which in our study represent the upper tail of the exposure
592 distributions in both simulation periods.

593

594 **8. Code and data availability**

595 The code and simulation results are available upon request
596 (spyros@chemeng.upatras.gr).

597

598 **9. Supplement**

599

600 **10. Author contributions**

601 P.G.R. and B.T.D. performed the PMCAMx simulations, analyzed the results and
602 wrote the manuscript. P.G.R. prepared the anthropogenic emissions and other inputs for
603 the simulations. I.K. set-up the WRF simulations and assisted in the preparation of the
604 meteorological inputs. S.N.P. and P.J.A. designed and coordinated the study and helped
605 in the writing of the paper. All authors reviewed and commented on the manuscript.

606

607 **11. Competing interests**

608 The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

609

610

611 **12. Financial Support**

612 This work was supported by the Center for Air, Climate, and Energy Solutions
613 (CACES) which was supported under Assistance Agreement No. R835873 awarded by the

614 U.S. Environmental Protection Agency and the Horizon-2020 Project REMEDIA of the
615 European Union under grant agreement No 874753.

616

617

618 **13. References**

- 619 Anand, S.: The concern for equity in health. *Journal of Epidemiology & Community Health*
620 56, 485–487, 2002.
- 621 Arunachalam, S., Holland, A., Do, B., Abraczinskas, M.: A quantitative assessment of the
622 influence of grid resolution on predictions of future-year air quality in North Carolina,
623 USA. *Atmospheric Environment* 40, 5010–5026, 2006.
- 624 Carter, W. P. L.: Documentation of the SAPRC-99 chemical mechanism for VOC
625 reactivity assessment, 1999.
- 626 Day, M., Pouliot, G., Hunt, S., Baker, K.R., Beardsley, M., Frost, G., Mobley, D., Simon,
627 H., Henderson, B., Yelverton, T., Rao, V.: Reflecting on progress since the 2005
628 NARSTO emissions inventory report. *Journal of the Air & Waste Management*
629 *Association* 69, 1025–1050, 2019.
- 630 Dockery, D. W., Pope, C. A.: Acute respiratory effects of particulate air pollution. *Annual*
631 *Review of Public Health* 15, 107–132, 1994.
- 632 Donahue N. M., Robinson, A. L., Stanier, C. O., Pandis, S. N.: Coupled partitioning,
633 dilution, and chemical aging of semivolatile organics. *Environmental Science &*
634 *Technology*, 40, 2635-2643, 2006.
- 635 Elessa Etuman, A., Coll, I.: OLYMPUS v1.0: Development of an integrated air pollutant
636 and GHG urban emissions model-methodology and calibration over greater Paris.
637 *Geoscientific Model Development* 11, 5085–5111, 2018.
- 638 ENVIRON: CAMx (Comprehensive Air Quality Model with Extensions) User's Guide
639 Version 4.20, 2005.
- 640 Eyth, A., Vukovich, J.: Technical Support Document (TSD): Preparation of Emissions
641 Inventories for the Version 6.2, 2011 Emissions Modeling Platform, 2016.
- 642 Fahey, K. M.; Pandis, S. N.: Optimizing model performance: variable size resolution in
643 cloud chemistry modeling. *Atmospheric Environment*, 35, 4471-4478, 2001.
- 644 Fountoukis, C., Koraj, D., Denier van der Gon, H. A. C., Charalampidis, P. E., Pilinis, C.,
645 Pandis, S. N.: Impact of grid resolution on the predicted fine PM by a regional 3-D
646 chemical transport model. *Atmospheric Environment* 68, 24–32, 2013.
- 647 Fountoukis, C., Racherla, P. N., Denier van der Gon, H. A. C., Polymeneas, P.,
648 Charalampidis, P. E., Pilinis, C., Wiedensohler, A., Dall'Osto, M., O'Dowd, C.,

649 Pandis, S. N.: Evaluation of a three-dimensional chemical transport model
650 (PMCAMx) in the European domain during the EUCAARI May 2008 campaign.
651 Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics 11, 10331–10347, 2011.

652 Gilliam, R. C., Pleim, J. E.: Performance assessment of new land surface and planetary
653 boundary layer physics in the WRF-ARW. Journal of Applied Meteorology and
654 Climatology 49, 760-774, 2010.

655 Gu, P., Li, H. Z., Ye, Q., Robinson, E. S., Apte, J. S., Robinson, A. L., Presto, A. A.:
656 Intracity variability of particulate matter exposure is driven by carbonaceous sources
657 and correlated with land-use variables. Environmental Science and Technology 52,
658 11545–11554, 2018.

659 Hogrefe, C., Pouliot, G., Wong, D., Torian, A., Roselle, S., Pleim, J., Mathur, R.: Annual
660 application and evaluation of the online coupled WRF-CMAQ system over North
661 America under AQMEII phase 2. Atmospheric Environment 115, 683–694, 2015.

662 Karydis, V. A., Tsimpidi, A. P., Fountoukis, C., Nenes, A., Zavala, M., Lei, W., Molina,
663 L. T., Pandis, S. N.: Simulating the fine and coarse inorganic particulate matter
664 concentrations in a polluted megacity. Atmospheric Environment 44, 608-620, 2010.

665 Kumar, N., Russell, A. G.: Multiscale air quality modeling of the Northeastern United
666 States. Atmospheric Environment 30, 1099–1116, 1996.

667 Lane, T. E., Donahue, N. M., Pandis, S. N.: Effect of NO_x on secondary organic aerosol
668 concentrations. Environmental Science & Technology 42, 6022–6027, 2008.

669 Ma, W., Pi, X., Qian, S.: Estimating multi-class dynamic origin-destination demand
670 through a forward-backward algorithm on computational graphs. Transportation
671 Research Part C: Emerging Technologies, 119, 102747, doi:10.1016/j.trc.2020.
672 102747, 2020.

673 McDonald, B., McBride, Z.: High-resolution mapping of motor vehicle carbon dioxide
674 emissions. Journal of Geophysical Research, 119, 5283–5298, 2014.

675 Murphy, B. N., Pandis, S. N.: Simulating the formation of semivolatile primary and
676 secondary organic aerosol in a regional chemical transport model. Environmental
677 Science & Technology, 43, 4722-4728, 2009.

678 Nenes A., Pandis, S. N., Pilinis, C.: ISORROPIA: A new thermodynamic equilibrium
679 model for multiphase multicomponent inorganic aerosols. Aquatic Geochemistry, 4,

680 123-152, 1998.

681 Pan, S., Choi, Y., Roy, A., Jeon, W.: Allocating emissions to 4 km and 1 km horizontal
682 spatial resolutions and its impact on simulated NO_x and O₃ in Houston, TX.
683 Atmospheric Environment 164, 398–415, 2017.

684 Pandis, S. N., Wexler, A. S., Seinfeld, J. H.: Secondary organic aerosol formation and
685 transport - II. Predicting the ambient secondary organic aerosol size distribution.
686 Atmospheric Environment, 27, 2403–2416, 1993.

687 Robinson, E. S., Gu, P., Ye, Q., Li, H. Z., Shah, R. U., Apte, J. S., Robinson, A. L., Presto,
688 A. A.: Restaurant impacts on outdoor air quality: Elevated organic aerosol mass from
689 restaurant cooking with neighborhood-scale plume extents. Environmental Science
690 and Technology 52, 9285–9294, 2018.

691 Rogers, R. E., Deng, A., Stauffer, D. R., Gaudet, B. J., Jia, Y., Soong, S. T., Tanrikulu, S.:
692 Application of the weather research and forecasting model for air quality modeling in
693 the San Francisco bay area. Journal of Applied Meteorology and Climatology 52,
694 1953–1973, 2013.

695 Seinfeld, J. H., Pandis, S. N.: Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics: From Air Pollution to
696 Climate Change, 2nd. ed. John Wiley & Sons, Inc., Hoboken, 2006.

697 Stroud, C. A., Makar, P. A., Moran, M. D., Gong, W., Gong, S., Zhang, J., Hayden, K.,
698 Mihele, C., Brook, J. R., Abbatt, J. P. D., Slowik, J. G.: Impact of model grid spacing
699 on regional- and urban-scale air quality predictions of organic aerosol. Atmospheric
700 Chemistry and Physics 11, 3107–3118, 2011.

701 Tsimpidi, A. P., Karydis, V. A., Zavala, M., Lei, W., Molina, L., Ulbrich, I. M., Jimenez,
702 J. L., Pandis, S. N.: Evaluation of the volatility basis-set approach for the simulation
703 of organic aerosol formation in the Mexico City metropolitan area. Atmospheric
704 Chemistry and Physics, 10, 525-546, 2010.

705 United States Environmental Protection Agency: 2011 National Emissions Inventory,
706 version 2 Technical Support Document, 2015.

707 Ye, Q., Gu, P., Li, H. Z., Robinson, E. S., Lipsky, E., Kaltsounoudis, C., Lee, A. K. Y.,
708 Apte, J. S., Robinson, A. L., Sullivan, R. C., Presto, A. A., Donahue, N. M.: Spatial
709 variability of sources and mixing state of atmospheric particles in a metropolitan area.
710 Environmental Science & Technology, 52, 6807-6815, 2018.

711 Zakoura, M., Pandis, S. N.: Improving fine aerosol nitrate predictions using a Plume-in-
712 Grid modeling approach. *Atmospheric Environment* 116887, doi:10.1016/j.atmosenv.
713 2019.116887, 2019.

714 Zakoura, M., Pandis, S. N.: Overprediction of aerosol nitrate by chemical transport
715 models: The role of grid resolution. *Atmospheric Environment* 187, 390–400, 2018.

716

717

718

719 **Table 1.** PM_{2.5} emissions by source for the 1 x 1 km Pittsburgh domain (February 2017).

720

Source Type	Emissions (kg d ⁻¹ km ⁻²)								
	PM _{2.5}	OA	EC	Chl.	Na	Amm.	Nitrate	Sulfate	Other
Agricultural dust	68.7	9.7	0.4	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.7	57.2
River barges	19.0	4.2	14.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1
Cooking	242	223	8.3	2.2	0.8	0.0	1.1	0.6	6.0
Misc. area sources	683	445	56.7	30.5	3.0	5.6	1.7	42	97.8
Off-road	147	56.2	73.1	0.3	0.1	0.0	0.3	1.1	16.1
Oil-gas (Area)	35.3	1.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	8.3	23.2
On-road traffic	188	84.6	75.2	0.3	0.1	1.8	0.6	8.3	16.4
Rail	40.7	8.9	31.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.2
Biomass burning	1,869	1,696	105	5.6	1.8	2.8	3.6	7.7	46.3
Power generation	3,517	201	194	2.8	0.0	15.7	2.6	460	2,641
Industrial	1,106	192	134	79.4	65.3	10.1	21.1	173	428
Oil-gas (point)	2.8	1.0	1.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.2	0.5

721

722 **Table 2.** PM_{2.5} emissions by source for the 1 x 1 km Pittsburgh domain (July 2017).

723

Source Type	Emissions (kg d ⁻¹ km ⁻²)								
	PM _{2.5}	OA	EC	Chl.	Na	Amm.	Nitrate	Sulfate	Other
Agricultural dust	67.3	8.9	0.4	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.7	56.9
River barges	19.0	4.2	14.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1
Cooking	242	223	8.3	2.2	0.8	0.0	1.1	0.6	6
Misc. area sources	593	392	49.1	28.5	2.5	5.3	1.1	33	81.6
Off-road	205	83.5	92.9	0.2	0.1	0.0	0.4	1.1	27.3
Oil-gas (Area)	35.9	1.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	8.9	25.0
On-road traffic	162	67.6	66	0.4	0.1	1.5	0.5	8.6	17.2
Rail	40.7	8.9	31.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.2
Biomass burning	24.3	22	1.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.6
Power generation	3,780	216	208	3.1	0.0	16.9	2.8	495	2,840
Industrial	1,050	188	133	67.3	56.2	9.9	21.0	165	412
Oil-gas (point)	2.8	1.0	1.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.2	0.5

724

725

726

727

728 **Figure 1.** Modeling domain used for the PMCAMx simulations. (A) 36 x 36 km
729 continental U.S. grid. (B) 12 x 12 and 4 x 4 km South Western Pennsylvania grids, and 1
730 x 1 km Pittsburgh nested grids.

731

732

733

734 **Figure 2.** Percentage of sector PM_{2.5} emissions in each 1x1 km computational cell for: (A)
735 commercial cooking and (B) on road traffic in February 2017. The value of the colored
736 points in each map add up to unity, corresponding to 100% of emissions for the respective
737 sector.

738

739

740

741

742 **Figure 3.** Average predicted ground-level concentration of total PM_{2.5}, EC, and OA at 36

743 x 36, 12 x 12, 4 x 4 and 1 x 1 km resolutions during February 2017. Different color scales

744 that do not start from zero are used for the various maps.

745

746

747

748

749 **Figure 4.** Average predicted ground-level concentration of PM_{2.5} sulfate, nitrate and
750 ammonium at a 36 x 36, 12 x 12, 4 x 4 and 1 x 1 km resolution during February 2017.

751 Different color scales that do not start from zero are used for the various maps.

752

753

755

756

757 **Figure 5.** Contribution of each source to total PM_{2.5} during February 2017. Different scales

758 are used for the various maps.

759

760

761

762 **Figure 6.** Average predicted concentration at the ground level of total $PM_{2.5}$, EC and OA
 763 at a 36x36, 12x12, 4x4 and 1x1 km during July 2017. Different color scales that do not
 764 start from zero are used for the various maps.

765

766

767

768

769 **Figure 7.** Average predicted concentration of PM_{2.5} sulfate, nitrate, and ammonium at a
770 36x36, 12x 12, 4x4 and 1x1 km during July 2017. Different color scales that do not start
771 from zero are used for the various maps.

772

773

774

775

776 **Figure 8.** Contribution of each source to total PM_{2.5} during July 2017. Different scales are

777 used for the various maps.

778

779

780

781 **Figure 9.** Relative contributions of local sources to average predicted total $PM_{2.5}$
 782 concentrations in the inner 1x1 km resolution domain during February and July 2017.

783

784

785 **Figure 10.** Relative contributions of local sources to average predicted PM_{2.5}
 786 concentrations at the location of highest average concentration (Beaver County) during
 787 February and July 2017.

788

789

790 **Figure 11.** Relative contributions of local sources to average predicted total PM_{2.5}
 791 concentrations in downtown Pittsburgh during February and July 2017.

792

794

795

796 **Figure 12.** Population exposure histograms at (A) 36x36, (B) 12x 12, (C) 4x4 and (D) 1x1
 797 km during February 2017. A different scale for population is used for the distribution at 36
 798 x 36 km resolution. The average population weighted PM_{2.5} concentration for each
 799 resolution is shown in the upper right corner of each window.

800

801
 802
 803
 804
 805
 806
 807

Figure 13. Population exposure histograms at (A) 36x36, (B) 12x 12, (C) 4x4 and (D) 1x1 km during July 2017. A different scale for population is used for the distribution at 36 x 36 km resolution. The average population weighted $PM_{2.5}$ concentration for each resolution is shown in the upper right corner of each window.

808
809

810
811
812
813

Figure 14. Relative contributions from local sources to population weighted total PM_{2.5} concentration for February and July 2017.